

Abutment-implant intermovement and corrosion. How the cone angle affects implant performance. An introduction to implant abutment connection classification, and the need to leave the platform switching concept behind and move forward

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon¹, David I Adam²

1 Ashty Teaching hospital
Erbil, Kurdistan region, Iraq
mzsmaxillofacial@gmail.com

2 OSTEOOTECH UK LIMITED
London – UK
davidibrahamadam@gmail.com

Abstract

Stress shielding and Titanium corrosion are the main issues that stand behind all titanium implants. Current concepts of the biocompatibility are mostly limited to the surface of the used material, rather than the stiffness or other mechanical criteria. The hub and shaft region of the dental implants had many regions. The most important region is the cone region. Cone angle affects the mechanical response of the implant and the resultant corrosion. Fretting corrosion remain the main issue in metallic hardware. In this introductory paper, we had represented 6 models to assess most of the current implant systems depending on the cone angle. The results show clearly the well-approved clinical issues especially platform switching concept. More models are needed to discern the complete picture.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, platform switching, platform matching, cone angle, Titanium corrosion, teeth, stiffness, bone,

Introduction

For long period of time the platform matching produces an unacceptable morbidity rate, namely osteolysis.

In their A meta-analysis (1), Chrcanovic, Bruno Ramos et al. stated many important things :

- The well observed association with bone loss
- (Most of them with short follow-up periods.) this statement denotes the manipulation of language in the research to cover our misunderstanding and rationalization of the commercial products. Using un accepted statements in the advertisement for products with long history of morbidities should be obsoleted

Figure 1 this is an example of advertisement in the 2025 for a product with long history of at least questionable performance. The same company produce another line and write it had platform switching

Again, another meta-analysis had also favor platform switching (2). This had been also without discussing the design criteria Another meta-analysis also includes close opinion (3).

AnyOne implant

- Implant – abatment connection 11°
- Recommended for immediate loading

‘Platform-Switching’ effect

Single prosthetic platform

Figure 2 the same company that declares the feature of platform switching is included in a product, the same company that produce the poor design

Absence of the engineering insight stand behind the production of platform-matching, which is like the original design of Brånemark, by many companies.

Almost all studies for Titanium dental had been totally misleading in comparison to those studies done for the Titanium hardware in arthroplasties. One of the most important two main issues are presented here, stress shielding and tribological properties regarding the design used in the dental implants. Many numerical studies of the dental implants studies emphasize design criteria and compare between different designs based on pointless futile criteria such as the maximum value of the Von mises stress

reached within the model (4). In their meta-analysis, Lakshmi.S indicated clearly that “ Platform switching for maintaining peri-implant bone levels has gained popularity over last few years. “ (5) “This study suggested that platform switching may have an indirect protective effect on implant hard tissue outcomes.” This what another metal-analysis had been ended with. (6).

The scientists had attributed the bone stability after shifting the design to the platform switching to three reasons (7).

- Thicker soft tissue cuff
- Less mobility closer to the bone
- Keeping the bacteria away from the bone

Many studies had been observed the different responses from different designs. These studies are numerical and physical. (8) (9)

Figure 3 small change in the dimension had been resulted in big difference. Lesser force arm and keeping the contact region away from the bone allowing he Titanium wear and tear product to be washed out by soft tissues. Again, this is not the good solution but it is just a remedy

These assumptions and explanations are totally away from the facts established in orthopedic surgery, where the corrosion and wear and tear accompanied by stress shielding would result in osteolysis. (10)

Corrosion is a dynamic process with a mechanical arm. (11) In the current paper, we want to establish a new methodology for the classification of dental implants. After a comprehensive evaluation, we had concluded that the dental abutment connection had these categories :

1. Best implant with gripping ability over the abutment with no need for connecting screw

2. Robust implant with gripping ability over the abutment and 2 points contact with horizontal force

3. Stable implant-abutment connection with 2 points of contact after horizontal load

4. Unstable Single contact implant-abutment with cone

5. Least stable single contact implant-abutment with flat surface, it is the original Brånemark design

Both the last 2 models had many similar features in terms of performance. The best ever invented product is the induction shrunk fin assembly. But this is not practical in the case of dental implants.

It is very disappointing that those the generations of oral surgeon had neglected the basis of the mechanical engineering and regarded the 4th design as a separate entity from the 5th design and sadly giving it a name called (INTERNAL HEX CONNECTION) deceiving the scientific community. When an engineer stands to correct the design, the medical community could reject his ideas and vice versa is correct.

Figure 4 Once approver says (fake it until you make it), some manufacturing make a shift in the abutment diameter at the connection to mimic platform switching when they incorporate a flat surface in the design

Our study is limited to 6 models. 90 models are highly suggested to be tested, each model represent a model with 1 degree increases from the previous model which will be in a separate project in the future if Almighty God will it will be.

The worst product to address the implant abutment gap formation due to the loading issues is the (Gap seal)

Figure 5 this is the one of poorest solution in implant dentistry

Gap seal literature had not been described the final fate of the product whether it will be solidified or remain viscous? And how it is behaving with the Titanium wear and tear tribology products and what about the third body wear.

Methodology, results and discussion

In this paper, we present a bold proposal. It is not an easy job for us and for the reader to catch the bird from the first shot. The next outlines are to pave the road for more detailed evaluations. We want to investigate the effect of the cone angle only and how this affects the :

- Connecting screw
- The interaction between the abutment and the implant specially regarding the stiffness
- The fatigue life of the implant
- The gap response between the implant and the abutment
- The contact pressure pattern between the abutment and the implant

How the abutment is behaving inside the implant ? The answer depends on the relationship between the cone walls. The cone represents the only contact region between the abutment and the implant in condition where the connecting screw produce compression between them. Preload is another object that is needed to be preserved. So, all the pressure will be transmitted at this region.

The cone must be the first evaluation criteria of any implant system

Figure 6 In the case of angled cone we have deformation that will eventually compress the abutment. While in the case of the platform matching all the force resulting from the connecting screw tightening will be converted to compression and exacerbate the corrosion of the surfaces

Figure 7 The behavior of the platform matching implant design is totally different from the deep platform matching design

Figure 8 The nature of the implant abutment connection in the case platform matching is angle on flat surface while in the case of deep connection the nature of contact is flat surface on flat surface. This is regarding the main contact region opposite to the force application site

Figure 9 The side opposite to the force application side in aid of friction provide additional stability feature that make the hub and shaft region derive its stability from the implant abutment connection itself rather than putting the connecting screw on exaggerated stresses

At which angle the transition from stable to unstable abutment should be investigated. This is called parametric approach.

Figure 10 The height of the cone will be reflected upon the implant wall height/base ration that role the deformability of the height of the implant vent wall . in the case of long wall and relatively thinner it will produce more favorable condition

Hot note

We should always remember that the selection of softer material (grade 4 Titanium) by vast majority of the companies to reduce the manufacturing cost. Deeper connection causing the manufacturing time to be higher and the cutting tools to be replaced more frequently as well as the stresses on the cutting tools to be raised due to the increase of the length between the holder and the cutting tool tip. We should always remember that the increase in the cutting tool will result in increase of the resonance magnitude of the tool which affect the machined surface finishing . Nevertheless, grade 4 titanium is better suited to make the implant from and the abutment from grade 5 from gradient of stiffness perspective

Figure 11 This is an example of 45 degrees cone angle. Surface area of the cone is about 6mm²

Figure 12 MAKING THE ANGLE different will change the cone surface area. In the previous example the cone angle of 9 degrees had nearly five folds larger surface area than the cone with 45 degrees angle

The larger surface area will result in less pressure in between the 2 surfaces. Ultimately, lead to less corrosion

There is no such thing that is called cold weld. The surface irregularities when 2 cones are pressed against each other will be interlocked and when the connecting screw is stopped from tightening, due to reaching the maximum tightening torque, will be aided by compression from the outer surface over the inner object leading to the inner object to stuck in its place.

Figure 13 When an implant with gripping properties had the connecting screw tightened the abutment will be stuck inside the implant. This is not due to the false futile claim of cold weld, but due to the friction aided by the strained connection

The line that separates the implant with gripping properties from the stable abutment type is the need for abutment removal tool as in the Figure 13. The best example for the ultimate gripping force is the induction shrunk fit holders used in holding end mills in the machining industry. They are manufacturing a holder that is slightly smaller in diameter than the cutting tool and when the machinist heats the holder for getting its expansion the tool could be inserted easily inside the holder. Then, when it cools down and the tool is inside it will exert a huge force on the tool preventing its pulling out.

Figure 14 The stained walls compress walls and with aid of friction this will grip the abutment inside the implant even after the connecting screw removal. And this explains the need for abutment removal tool in some of the products of Trate, Maco and Megagen and Biotec implants

The contact of the platform switching is an angle on flat surface. Even with the model of less favorable angle which we had called it the unstable abutment with cone, the stresses transfer from the abutment to the implant is less favorable. Nevertheless, the performance is totally different.

Figure 15 The design criteria are true dilemma. The angle of the cone here is 45 degrees. First model on the left had the least favorable results

Figure 16 The design dilemma in result in wide varieties of the products in the market. The angle of the cone here is more acute than the model in the Figure 15

How we should select the design? This should be approached parametrically. The resultant performance is a combination between stiffness of the walls and the tribological features of the implant.

Figure 17 this model is behaving like ball and socket connection although it is flat but it lead to the same result

Figure 18 The design of the screw also had an effect on the stiffness of the implant. All the 3 models are exactly the same away from the connecting screw and its vent

The connecting screw had a very important effect on the implant performance, but to which extent this effect is apparent? it needs more clarification. This needs a separate paper. The next design's purpose is highlighting the effect of the design criteria on the performance of the implant systems.

In all implant design of the 2 pieces there will be some sort of corrosion. Fretting corrosion and the crevicular corrosion is the integral part of the 2-piece design drawbacks. These issues is reduced by wise selection of the implant design.

It is prudent to select the design that is better and don't say this implant system is good because the dealer provides all the needed accessories.

From biomechanical point of view, we had these criteria of evaluations of the dental implant systems:

- Ability of the hub and shaft region to transfer the stresses to the implant body region and to the surrounding bone to enhance stresses transfer and preclude stress shield.
- The design should reduce the Titanium corrosion effect.
- The balance between stiffness and strength should result in higher fatigue resistance.
- The design should address the connecting screw loosening issue.
- The main purpose of the 2 pieces design is to make prosthodontic rehabilitation practical and safer as well as closer to the single piece design.

We had made a model similar to the model used in our recently published paper. (12) The boundaries conditions had been replicated and we had additional tested situation which is the rotating force.

Figure 19 in the previous paper we had discussed the green region. Now we are discussing the red region

Figure 20 the base is fixed and the circle represent the application of the force

Figure 21 according to the authors knowledge, there are no comprehensive products had been produced by any company that reach the level of Bicon company products. The best model is like Bicon model from our point of view.

Figure 22 Roott implant had total angle 10.3 degrees, Megagen any ridge 10 degrees, Macco conical active 8 degrees, Biotec Conical Connection | B1 had 10 degrees

No calibration of the needed removal torque among the 4 main models in the Figure 22 as well as no calculation of the cone surface area of the models in the Figure 22. The previous 4 models need more evaluation based on the other geometrical criteria.

In some of the studied models, the connecting screw had been shorter than other models. This needs deeper investigation through parametric approach. We attribute the connecting screw loosening due to :

- The deformation and resulting plasticity due to loading followed by deloading. Loading in many cases with poor design will lead to exaggerated stresses leading to elongation of the screw shaft and deformation of the threads
- The plasticity in the thread's region is due to the shear strain while at the shaft is due to the tension

Figure 23 at the threads region the strain will be shear mostly while at the shaft it is mostly tensile

- The flattening of the contact regions (between the connecting screw and both the abutment at the head region and the implant at the threads regions) after loading and deloading. These contact regions are not totally flat due to the manufacturing consideration
- The complex nature of the implant abutment loading (rotation + lateral force) leading to the screw to be rotated in loosening direction.
Many implantologists don't address these issues. We had heard about cementing the connecting screw during tightening which is highly contraindicating maneuver.

Ho to evaluate the implant

- The ration of the abutment implant displacement
- The displacement of the model
- The contact pressure
- X displacement
-etc.

We had studied these models

- ✚ Bicon like model which is the best implant with gripping ability over the abutment with no need for connecting screw
- ✚ The 4 models in the Figure 22 had been , where they are robust implants with gripping ability over the abutment and 2 points contact with horizontal force

- ✚ Dual contacts at horizontal loading where these models are stable implant-abutment connection with 2 points of contact after horizontal load
- ✚ Design of single cone, but single contact at lateral load which represents an unstable design
- ✚ Flat surface connection (platform matching like connection) which is the least stable single contact implant-abutment with flat surface, it is the original Brånemark design. Both the last 2 models had many similar features in design and common things in the terms of performance.

Figure 24 these are the used models. The holder and force application regions are identical across all the models. Relationship of the holder to the implant body are the same across all models

Figure 25 The green region represents the contact region of the implant abutment connection. The connecting screws are identical in all models, but just different in length of the connecting screw shaft

Figure 26 the upper regions away from the contact with the abutment, screw threads region and the spline region are all identical across all the models

There are many systems that mimics Bicon like model. We hadn't chosen IM Macon form Maco due to many biomechanical and practical issues. At least we couldn't find sound evidence of dimension as well as many objections on the design of the implant and the abutment as well as the instruments. As we hadn't contacted any dealer, we hadn't contacted the dealer also for the Macco system.

Bicon is a screwless system. Nevertheless, the current model had been represented as screwed model to make some sort of similarity to the other current models. Bicon solid abutment with screw like extension at the bottom. Although this design is highly different from the bicon design, but it hires the main design criteria of the bicon (solid abutment + cone angle) and compared it to the other designs.

In the current models the aim was to highlight the differences rather than defining the exact border where the subtype of the abutment START or shift from a type to another

Figure 27 this is the cone angle which had been represented previously in 3D figures

Figure 28 cone angle of 20 degrees

In their recent publication on the official website about the design with platform matching, Noble BioCare had stated that it is “Established and clinically proven – the most scientifically documented implant system in the world, in clinical use for more than 45 years” which is highly erroneous statement as this design is the poorest design ever had been created (13)

Again, we hadn't characterized the line that separate between all these designs. This needs a separate paper. We want to define the main concept behind each design

Criteria of evaluation

We had tested these criteria :

- To test the effect of the screw tightening we test the screw pretension
- To test the effect of the mechanical loading we added the horizontal force in the direction of the coordination system
- To see the effect on the screw loosening as well as the complex loading conditions we test lateral force and rotation in same time. The model of 45 degrees had been exposed to slightly less force due to the resulted high instability

Figure 29 Megagen company had 3 totally different designs indicating the loss of the leading compass and absence of the engineering insight. We should always emphasize on the fact that the stability of the implant with upper flat design is connecting screw derived. This is in contrast with the stabilizing competent cone.

The results

Regarding Displacement, when the screw is tightened, the abutment will act as a wedge inside the implant to evaluate this feature we will.

Figure 30 Displacement bicon like model after just tightening 6.8545

Figure 31 Displacement 4.5 degrees model just tightening 52.822×10^{-6} . The displacement pattern of this model is resembling the displacement pattern of the previous (bicon like model). This is the clear representation of the implant abutment gripping model.

Figure 32 Displacement 9 degrees model after just tightening 466.27×10^{-6} . This model had less concentric and tilted resulting in higher displacement. The Z displacement field will reveal better evaluation of the model

Figure 33 Displacement 20 degrees model after just tightening 183.79×10^{-6}

Figure 34 Displacement 45 degrees model just tightening 156.64×10^{-18}

Figure 35 Displacement 89 degrees model just tightening 30.695×10^{-9} . We hadn't able to make 90-degree model which is equal to Brånemark model

Displacement bicon like model just tightening $6.8545 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Displacement 4.5 degrees model just tightening $5.2822 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Displacement 9 degrees model just tightening $46.6.27 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Displacement 20 degrees model just tightening $18.379 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Displacement 45 degrees model just tightening $156.64 \cdot 10^{-18}$

Displacement 89 degrees model just tightening $30.695 \cdot 10^{-9}$

Total displacement needs more additional criteria to discern the total picture. These criteria are

- Z displacement to see the true downward movement of the abutment
- X and y displacement to see the implant widening regions

Next graphs is to give an engineering representation of the reactionary results

Figure 36 Contact force of the bicon like abutment after tightening

Figure 37 Contact force of the 4.5 degrees model abutment after tightening

Figure 38 Contact force 9 degrees model

Figure 39 contact force of the 20 degrees model

Figure 40 Contact force of the 45-degree model. the results here are odd

Figure 41 Contact force 89-degree model

Figure 42 Z displacement of the bicon like model

Figure 43 Z displacement of the 4.5 degrees model

Figure 44 Z displacement of the 9 degrees model

Figure 45 Z displacement of the 20 degrees model

Figure 46 Z displacement of the 45 degrees model

Figure 47 Z displacement of the 89 degrees model

Figure 48 Bicon like design strain. The strain at the upper surface is totally scarce

Figure 49 4.5-degree model strain after just tightening of the connecting screw. The least strain at the upper surface indicates the deeper surface to surface contact which is a very helpful condition

Figure 50 9-degree model strain after just tightening of the connecting screw. More strain at the upper surface indicating the totally less favorable condition

Figure 51 20-degree model strain after just tightening of the connecting screw

The next 2 figures are just for the body of the implants to investigate the strains further.

Figure 52 45-degree model strain after just tightening of the connecting screw

Figure 53 89-degree model strain after just tightening of the connecting screw

The closed proximity of the 45 and semi flat model (as the angle is 89 degrees and not true 90 degrees) indicates how much both designs are poor in the term of biomechanical performances. Other models had prominent wedging effect. This effect aid in stabilizing the abutment. All the next models had tightening and lateral force. Absence of the last 2 models from the pattern of the first 4 models indicating the ability of the abutment to widen the implant and getting more stability.

Figure 54 With lateral force bicon like model

Figure 55 With lateral force Model with 4.5 degree

Figure 56 With lateral force Model with 9 degrees. The pattern began to be more clear and the narrowing of the transitional zone from the high to low displacement

Figure 57 With lateral force Model with 20 degrees. The abutment is totally unstable

Figure 58 With lateral force Model with 45 degrees. The center of rotation is began to shift from its centra position

Figure 59 With lateral force Model with 89 degrees. The 20 and 45 model allow for rotation of the abutment inside the implant

Figure 60 the change in the displacement pattern is apparent. For the first glance the bicon like model is close to the platform matching model but the deeper investigation and inclusion of other criteria will show the complete picture

The relative displacement between the implant and the abutment indicates simply the sliding between each other and the accompanied fretting corrosion and tear and wear

Always, we should remember the poor tribological of the Titanium alloys (14)

Figure 61 Hub and shaft region depth cause significant amount of the ability of the implant straining which should be correlated correctly to the cone angle and the preload of the connecting screw

Figure 62 With lateral force Cross section of the bicon like model displacement. Minimum gap had been formed

Figure 63 Previous model implant only

Figure 64 With lateral force Cross section of the 4.5-degree model displacement

Figure 65 Previous model implant only

Figure 66 With lateral force Cross section of the 9 degree model displacement

Figure 67 Previous model only the implant

Figure 68 With lateral force Cross section of the 20 degree model displacement

The difference between the 20 and 45 model indicate the deeper investigation of the parametric correlation between the inclination and the resultant displacement

Figure 69 Previous model only the implant

Figure 70 With lateral force Cross section of the 45-degree model displacement. Relative rotation allows for more discontinuity at the force application side.

Figure 71 Previous model only the implant

Figure 72 With lateral force Cross section of the 89-degrees model displacement

Figure 73 Previous model only the implant. We could assume that the flat connection could be better than the poorly configured implant . Another model of lateral force and tightening to explore the effect of the connection on the possible corrosion resulted

Figure 74 Bicon like model the contact pressure is apparent

Figure 75 Bicon like model gap between the abutment and the implant. This dual contact stand behind the good performance of the implant

Figure 76 Model of 4.5 angle contact pressure

Figure 77 Model of 4.5 angle gap distance. In the 4.5 model the contact will be lesser than bicon like model and the gap also start to become higher

Figure 78 Model of 9 degrees angle contact pressure. The contact start be 2 separated regions

Figure 79 Gap of the mode 9 degrees is much higher than the 2 previous models. The gap tend to have one continuous region

Figure 80 Model of 20 degrees angle contact pressure

Figure 81 Gap of the mode 20 degrees is much higher than the previous models. The gap in the force application site and other side become continuous

Figure 82 Contact pressure of the 45 degrees model

Figure 83 The gap of 45 degrees model is totally different from the other models

Figure 84 Contact pressure of the flat model (Brånemark model)

Figure 85 Gap of the flat model. We must always emphasize the patter of distribution and connect it to other evaluation criteria to get the whole picture

The issues associated with the connecting screw are

- The imperfection of the manufacturing that lead to micro-irregular surface and after tightening and loosening there will be more flat and harder surface
- The plastic deformation that occurs at the threads area (mostly shear at the base of the thread) and at the shaft (mostly tensile)
- The configuration of the head in relation to the abutment, the design criteria of dimensions and the material and manufacturing technique

To see the effect of the design on the connecting screw shaft we should seek for the 1st principal strain

Figure 86 1st principal strain with bicon like model. This is partially due to configuration of the boundaries conditions of the used model

Figure 87 1st principal strain with 4.5 degrees model . The implant abutment gripping will protect the screw from the plastic change by forcing the implant body to deform which is equal to more stress transfer from abutment to the abutment

Figure 88 1st principal strain with 9 degrees model. The strain along all the side of the shaft

Figure 89 1st principal strain with 20 degrees model

Figure 90 1st principal strain with 45 degrees model

Figure 91 1st principal strain with flat like design

Figure 92 The von Mises stress of the bicon like design lateral force and rotation.

The stress from 2 region:

- From the walls
- From the screw

So that the abutment either retrieve its stability from the friction with the wall or from the dependence on the connecting screw. The nature of the complex loading conditions leads to more pronounced effect of the poor abutment implant connection configuration on the screw loosening.

Figure 93 The v mises stress of the 4.5 degrees angle lateral force and rotation

Figure 94 The v mises stress of the 9 degrees angle lateral force and rotation

Figure 95 The von Mises stress of the 20 degrees angle lateral force and rotation

Figure 96 The von Mises stress of the 45 degrees angle lateral force and rotation

Figure 97 The v mises stress of the flat design variant lateral force and rotation

Figure 98 transition of the stresses is apparent across all the model. The model on the left is the bicon like model then the 9 degrees model then the 20 degrees model then the original platform matching model. We had not represented the 4.5 and 45degrees models.

Figure 99 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 4.5 degrees model. In the bicon like model the shaft of the connecting screw is very short

Figure 100 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 4.5 degrees model

Figure 101 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 9 degrees model

Figure 102 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 20 degrees model

Figure 103 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 45 degrees model

Figure 104 2nd principal strain of the connecting screw shaft of the 89 degrees model

Figure 105 2nd principal strain of the implant body in bicon like design with lateral force and rotation

Figure 106 2nd principal strain of the implant body in 4.5 degrees design with lateral force and rotation

Figure 107 2nd principal strain of the implant body in 9 degrees design with lateral force and rotation

Figure 108 2nd principal strain of the implant body in 20 degrees design with lateral force and rotation

Volume: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 109 2nd principal strain of the implant body in 45 degrees design with lateral force and rotation

Figure 110 2nd principal strain of the implant body in 89 degrees design with lateral force and rotation

Figure 111 Curl of the displacement, z component of the bicon like design

Figure 112 Curl of the displacement, z component of the 4.5 degrees model

Figure 113 Curl of the displacement, z component of the 9 degrees model

Figure 114 Curl of the displacement, z component of the 20 degrees model

Figure 115 Curl of the displacement, z component of the 45 degrees model

Figure 116 Curl of the displacement, z component of the 89 degrees model. We had compared between the rotation action only of 4.5 and 9 and 20 degrees model

Figure 117 Rotation of the models from right to left 4.5 degrees 9 degrees 20 degrees. The displacement is higher with the higher angle and less uniform

Figure 118 Rotation of the implant model only models from right to left 4.5 degrees 9 degrees 20 degrees. The displacement becomes more uniform and higher with the less angle

Figure 119 2nd principal strain of the shaft of the connecting screw indicating the possible screw loosening due to the Rotation of the models from right to left 4.5 degrees 9 degrees 20 degrees.

Figure 120 The 2nd principal strain of the implant only from the case of the from right to left 4.5 degrees 9 degrees 20 degrees. Indicating the higher ability of the abutment to rotate the implant with less screw loosening results. These results indicate the more robust implant abutment connection in stresses transmission

Figure 121 Y field of displacement of the models from right to left 4.5 degrees 9 degrees 20 degrees the less is the better. We hadn't modeled the y field of displacement of only implant

The last issue to be evaluated is the estimation of the fatigue life of the dental implant. We had chosen the strain energy criteria to evaluate this issue. The chosen condition was the tightened abutment with lateral force

Figure 122 Stran energy density of the bicon like design

Figure 123 strain energy density of the 4.5 degrees model

Figure 124 strain energy density of the 9 degrees model

Figure 125 strain energy density of the 20 degrees model

Figure 126 strain energy density of the 45 degrees model

Figure 127 strain energy density of the 89 degrees model

Figure 128 the transition of the strain energy distribution in the different designs is apparent. The 2nd and 3rd model had marked 2 walls involvement. The last design act as a lever with sole resistance that is derived from the connecting screw. The increase in the angle of the cone coincides with increase in the energy density in the connecting screw

The nature of the contact between the abutment and the implant in accordance with its geometrical configuration show us the higher wear and tear in the last 3 models on the right

Figure 129 3D representation of the strain energy density of the bicon like model

Figure 130 3D representation of the strain energy density of the 4.5 model

Figure 131 3D representation of the strain energy density of the 9 degrees model

Figure 132 3D representation of the strain energy density of the 20 degrees model

Figure 133 3D representation of the strain energy density of the 45 degrees model

Figure 134 3D representation of the strain energy density of the 89 degrees model

Figure 135 in the last figure the absence of the strain energy density at the outermost region of the upper surface away from the region of the contact with the abutment indicate the deleterious effect of the compression came from the abutment

We admit that our model in many of the models is highly stiff and the body diameter is high rendering the demonstration of many features in the body response difficult to be evaluated. Nevertheless, such model is highly desirable to test the hub and shaft region parametrically. We should consider the implant to be exposed to repetitive stresses that will erode the surface by time resulting in loss of the fitness and more freedom in interparts-movement where the screw frequent loosening could be partially explained by this issue.

Table of the figures

FIGURE 1 THIS IS AN EXAMPLE OF ADVERTISEMENT IN THE 2025 FOR A PRODUCT WITH LONG HISTORY OF AT LEAST QUESTIONABLE PERFORMANCE. THE SAME COMPANY PRODUCE ANOTHER LINE AND WRITE IT HAD PLATFORM SWITCHING	121
FIGURE 2 THE SAME COMPANY THAT DECLARES THE FEATURE OF PLATFORM SWITCHING IS INCLUDED IN A PRODUCT, THE SAME COMPANY THAT PRODUCE THE POOR DESIGN	121
FIGURE 3 SMALL CHANGE IN THE DIMENSION HAD BEEN RESULTED IN BIG DIFFERENCE. LESSER FORCE ARM AND KEEPING THE CONTACT REGION AWAY FROM THE BONE ALLOWING HE TITANIUM WEAR AND TEAR PRODUCT TO BE WASHED OUT BY SOFT TISSUES. AGAIN, THIS IS NOT THE GOOD SOLUTION BUT IT IS JUST A REMEDY	122
FIGURE 4 ONCE APPROVER SAYS (FAKE IT UNTIL YOU MAKE IT), SOME MANUFACTURING MAKE A SHIFT IN THE ABUTMENT DIMETER AT THE CONNECTION TO MIMIC PLATFORM SWITCHING WHEN THEY INCORPORATE A FLAT SURFACE IN THE DESIGN	123
FIGURE 5 THIS IS THE ONE OF POOREST SOLUTION IN IMPLANT DENTISTRY	124
FIGURE 6 IN THE CASE OF ANGLED CONE WE HAVE DEFORMATION THAT WILL EVENTUALLY COMPRESS THE ABUTMENT. WHILE IN THE CASE OF THE PLATFORM MATCHING ALL THE FORCE RESULTING FROM THE CONNECTING SCREW TIGHTENING WILL BE CONVERTED TO COMPRESSION AND EXACERBATE THE CORROSION OF THE SURFACES	125
FIGURE 7 THE BEHAVIOR OF THE PLATFORM MATCHING IMPLANT DESIGN IS TOTALLY DIFFERENT FROM THE DEEP PLATFORM MATCHING DESIGN	125
FIGURE 8 THE NATURE OF THE IMPLANT ABUTMENT CONNECTION IN THE CASE PLATFORM MATCHING IS ANGLE ON FLAT SURFACE WHILE IN THE CASE OF DEEP CONNECTION THE NATURE OF CONTACT IS FLAT SURFACE ON FLAT SURFACE. THIS IS REGARDING THE MAIN CONTACT REGION OPPOSITE TO THE FORCE APPLICATION SITE	126
FIGURE 9 THE SIDE OPPOSITE TO THE FORCE APPLICATION SIDE IN AID OF FRICTION PROVIDE ADDITIONAL STABILITY FEATURE THAT MAKE THE HUB AND SHAFT REGION DERIVE ITS STABILITY FROM THE IMPLANT ABUTMENT CONNECTION ITSELF RATHER THAN PUTTING THE CONNECTING SCREW ON EXAGGERATED STRESSES	126
FIGURE 10 THE HEIGHT OF THE CONE WILL BE REFLECTED UPON THE IMPLANT WALL HEIGHT/BASE RATION THAT ROLE THE DEFORMABILITY OF THE HEIGHT OF THE IMPLANT VENT WALL . IN THE CASE OF LONG WALL AND RELATIVELY THINNER IT WILL PRODUCE MORE FAVORABLE CONDITION	127
FIGURE 11 THIS IS AN EXAMPLE OF 45 DEGREES CONE ANGLE. SURFACE AREA OF THE CONE IS ABOUT 6MM ²	128
FIGURE 12 MAKING THE ANGLE DIFFERENT WILL CHANGE THE CONE SURFACE AREA. IN THE PREVIOUS EXAMPLE THE CONE ANGLE OF 9 DEGREES HAD NEARLY FIVE FOLDS LARGER SURFACE AREA THAN THE CONE WITH 45 DEGREES ANGLE	128
FIGURE 13 WHEN AN IMPLANT WITH GRIPPING PROPERTIES HAD THE CONNECTING SCREW TIGHTENED THE ABUTMENT WILL BE STUCK INSIDE THE IMPLANT. THIS IS NOT DUE TO THE FALSE FUTILE CLAIM OF COLD WELD, BUT DUE TO THE FRICTION AIDED BY THE STRAINED CONNECTION	129
FIGURE 14 THE STAINED WALLS COMPRESS WALLS AND WITH AID OF FRICTION THIS WILL GRIP THE ABUTMENT INSIDE THE IMPLANT EVEN AFTER THE CONNECTING SCREW REMOVAL. AND THIS EXPLAINS THE NEED FOR ABUTMENT REMOVAL TOOL IN SOME OF THE PRODUCTS OF TRATE, MACO AND MEGAGEN AND BIOTEC IMPLANTS	129
FIGURE 15 THE DESIGN CRITERIA ARE TRUE DILEMMA. THE ANGLE OF THE CONE HERE IS 45 DEGREES. FIRST MODEL ON THE LEFT HAD THE LEAST FAVORABLE RESULTS	130

FIGURE 16 THE DESIGN DILEMMA IN RESULT IN WIDE VARIETIES OF THE PRODUCTS IN THE MARKET. THE ANGLE OF THE COME HERE IS MORE ACUTE THAN THE MODEL IN THE FIGURE 10	131
FIGURE 17 THIS MODEL IS BEHAVING LIKE BALLED CONNECTION ALTHOUGH IT IS FLAT BUT IT LEAD TO THE SAME RESULT	132
FIGURE 18 THE DESIGN OF THE SCREW ALSO HAD AN EFFECT ON THE STIFFNESS OF THE IMPLANT. ALL THE 3 MODELS ARE EXACTLY THE SAME AWAY FROM THE CONNECTING SCREW AND ITS VENT	132
FIGURE 19 IN THE PREVIOUS PAPER WE HAD DISCUSSED THE GREEN REGION. NOW WE ARE DISCUSSING THE RED REGION	133
FIGURE 20 THE BASE IS FIXED AND THE CIRCLE REPRESENT THE APPLICATION OF THE FORCE	134
FIGURE 21 ACCORDING TO THE AUTHORS KNOWLEDGE, THERE ARE NO COMPREHENSIVE PRODUCTS HAD BEEN PRODUCED BY ANY COMPANY THAT REACH THE LEVEL OF BICON COMPANY PRODUCTS. THE BEST MODEL IS LIKE BICON MODEL FROM OUR POINT OF VIEW.	135
FIGURE 22 ROOTT IMPLANT HAD TOTAL ANGLE 10.3 DEGREES, MEGAGEN ANY RIDGE 10 DEGREES, MACCO CONICAL ACTIVE 8 DEGREES, BIOTEC CONICAL CONNECTION B1 HAD 10 DEGREES	136
FIGURE 23 AT THE THREADS REGION THE STRAIN WILL BE SHEAR MOSTLY WHILE AT THE SHAFT IT IS MOSTLY TENSILE	137
FIGURE 24 THESE ARE THE USED MODELS. THE HOLDER AND FORCE APPLICATION REGIONS ARE IDENTICAL ACROSS ALL THE MODELS. RELATIONSHIP OF THE HOLDER TO THE IMPLANT BODY ARE THE SAME ACROSS ALL MODELS	138
FIGURE 25 THE GREEN REGION REPRESENTS THE CONTACT REGION OF THE IMPLANT ABUTMENT CONNECTION. THE CONNECTING SCREWS ARE IDENTICAL IN ALL MODELS, BUT JUST DIFFERENT IN LENGTH OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT	138
FIGURE 26 THE UPPER REGIONS AWAY FROM THE CONTACT WITH THE ABUTMENT, SCREW THREADS REGION AND THE SPLINE REGION ARE ALL IDENTICAL ACROSS ALL THE MODELS	139
FIGURE 27 THIS IS THE CONE ANGLE WHICH HAD BEEN REPRESENTED PREVIOUSLY IN 3D FIGURES	140
FIGURE 28 CONE ANGLE OF 20 DEGREES	140
FIGURE 29 MEGAGEN COMPANY HAD 3 TOTALLY DIFFERENT DESIGNS INDICATING THE LOSS OF THE LEADING COMPASS AND ABSENCE OF THE ENGINEERING INSIGHT. WE SHOULD ALWAYS EMPHASIZE ON THE FACT THAT THE STABILITY OF THE IMPLANT WITH UPPER FLAT DESIGN IS CONNECTING SCREW DERIVED. THIS IS IN CONTRAST WITH THE STABILIZING COMPETENT CONE.	141
FIGURE 30 DISPLACEMENT BICON LIKE MODEL AFTER JUST TIGHTENING 6.8545	143
FIGURE 31 DISPLACEMENT 4.5 DEGREES MODEL JUST TIGHTENING $52.822 \cdot 10^{-6}$. THE DISPLACEMENT PATTERN OF THIS MODEL IS RESEMBLING THE DISPLACEMENT PATTERN OF THE PREVIOUS (BICON LIKE MODEL). THIS IS THE CLEAR REPRESENTATION OF THE IMPLANT ABUTMENT GRIPPING MODEL.	144
FIGURE 32 DISPLACEMENT 9 DEGREES MODEL AFTER JUST TIGHTENING $466.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$. THIS MODEL HAD LESS CONCENTRIC AND TILTED RESULTING IN HIGHER DISPLACEMENT. THE Z DISPLACEMENT FIELD WILL REVEAL BETTER EVALUATION OF THE MODEL	145
FIGURE 33 DISPLACEMENT 20 DEGREES MODEL AFTER JUST TIGHTENING $183.79 \cdot 10^{-6}$	146
FIGURE 34 DISPLACEMENT 45 DEGREES MODEL JUST TIGHTENING $156.64 \cdot 10^{-18}$	147
FIGURE 35 DISPLACEMENT 89 DEGREES MODEL JUST TIGHTENING $30.695 \cdot 10^{-9}$. WE HADN'T ABLE TO MAKE 90-DEGREE MODEL WHICH IS EQUAL TO BRÅNEMARK MODEL	148
FIGURE 36 CONTACT FORCE OF THE BICON LIKE ABUTMENT AFTER TIGHTENING	150
FIGURE 37 CONTACT FORCE OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL ABUTMENT AFTER TIGHTENING	151
FIGURE 38 CONTACT FORCE 9 DEGREES MODEL	152
FIGURE 39 CONTACT FORCE OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	153

FIGURE 40 CONTACT FORCE OF THE 45-DEGREE MODEL. THE RESULTS HERE ARE ODD	154
FIGURE 41 CONTACT FORCE 89-DEGREE MODEL	155
FIGURE 42 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE BICON LIKE MODEL	156
FIGURE 43 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL	157
FIGURE 44 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE 9 DEGREES MODEL	158
FIGURE 45 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	159
FIGURE 46 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	160
FIGURE 47 Z DISPLACEMENT OF THE 89 DEGREES MODEL	161
FIGURE 48 BICON LIKE DESIGN STRAIN. THE STRAIN AT THE UPPER SURFACE IS TOTALLY SCARCE	162
FIGURE 49 4.5-DEGREE MODEL STRAIN AFTER JUST TIGHTENING OF THE CONNECTING SCREW. THE LEAST STRAIN AT THE UPPER SURFACE INDICATES THE DEEPER SURFACE TO SURFACE CONTACT WHICH IS A VERY HELPFUL CONDITION	163
FIGURE 50 9-DEGREE MODEL STRAIN AFTER JUST TIGHTENING OF THE CONNECTING SCREW. MORE STRAIN AT THE UPPER SURFACE INDICATING THE TOTALLY LESS FAVORABLE CONDITION	164
FIGURE 51 20-DEGREE MODEL STRAIN AFTER JUST TIGHTENING OF THE CONNECTING SCREW	165
FIGURE 52 45-DEGREE MODEL STRAIN AFTER JUST TIGHTENING OF THE CONNECTING SCREW	166
FIGURE 53 89-DEGREE MODEL STRAIN AFTER JUST TIGHTENING OF THE CONNECTING SCREW	167
FIGURE 54 WITH LATERAL FORCE BICON LIKE MODEL	169
FIGURE 55 WITH LATERAL FORCE MODEL WITH 4.5 DEGREE	170
FIGURE 56 WITH LATERAL FORCE MODEL WITH 9 DEGREES. THE PATTERN BEGAN TO BE MORE CLEAR AND THE NARROWING OF THE TRANSITIONAL ZONE FROM THE HIGH TO LOW DISPLACEMENT	171
FIGURE 57 WITH LATERAL FORCE MODEL WITH 20 DEGREES. THE ABUTMENT IS TOTALLY UNSTABLE	172
FIGURE 58 WITH LATERAL FORCE MODEL WITH 45 DEGREES. THE CENTER OF ROTATION IS BEGAN TO SHIFT FROM ITS CENTRA POSITION	173
FIGURE 59 WITH LATERAL FORCE MODEL WITH 89 DEGREES. THE 20 AND 45 MODEL ALLOW FOR ROTATION OF THE ABUTMENT INSIDE THE IMPLANT	174
FIGURE 60 THE CHANGE IN THE DISPLACEMENT PATTERN IS APPARENT. FOR THE FIRST GLANCE THE BICON LIKE MODEL IS CLOSE TO THE PLATFORM MATCHING MODEL BUT THE DEEPER INVESTIGATION AND INCLUSION OF OTHER CRITERIA WILL SHOW THE COMPLETE PICTURE	175
FIGURE 61 HUB AND SHAFT REGION DEPTH CAUSE SIGNIFICANT AMOUNT OF THE ABILITY OF THE IMPLANT STRAINING WHICH SHOULD BE CORRELATED CORRECTLY TO THE CONE ANGLE AND THE PRELOAD OF THE CONNECTING SCREW	175
FIGURE 62 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE BICON LIKE MODEL DISPLACEMENT. MINIMUM GAP HAD BEEN FORMED	176
FIGURE 63 PREVIOUS MODEL IMPLANT ONLY	177
FIGURE 64 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE 4.5-DEGREE MODEL DISPLACEMENT	178
FIGURE 65 PREVIOUS MODEL IMPLANT ONLY	179
FIGURE 66 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE 9 DEGREE MODEL DISPLACEMENT	180
FIGURE 67 PREVIOUS MODEL ONLY THE IMPLANT	181
FIGURE 68 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE 20 DEGREE MODEL DISPLACEMENT	182
FIGURE 69 PREVIOUS MODEL ONLY THE IMPLANT	184
FIGURE 70 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE 45-DEGREE MODEL DISPLACEMENT. RELATIVE ROTATION ALLOWS FOR MORE DISCONTINUITY AT THE FORCE APPLICATION SIDE.	185
FIGURE 71 PREVIOUS MODEL ONLY THE IMPLANT	186
FIGURE 72 WITH LATERAL FORCE CROSS SECTION OF THE 89-DEGREES MODEL DISPLACEMENT	187

FIGURE 73 PREVIOUS MODEL ONLY THE IMPLANT. WE COULD ASSUME THAT THE FLAT CONNECTION COULD BE BETTER THAN THE POORLY CONFIGURATED IMPLANT . ANOTHER MODEL OF LATERAL FORCE AND TIGHTENING TO EXPLORE THE EFFECT OF THE CONNECTION ON THE POSSIBLE CORROSION RESULTED	188
FIGURE 74 BICON LIKE MODEL THE CONTACT PRESSURE IS APPARENT	189
FIGURE 75 BICON LIKE MODEL GAP BETWEEN THE ABUTMENT AND THE IMPLANT. THIS DUAL CONTACT STAND BEHIND THE GOOD PERFORMANCE OF THE IMPLANT	190
FIGURE 76 MODEL OF 4.5 ANGLE CONTACT PRESSURE	191
FIGURE 77 MODEL OF 4.5 ANGLE GAP DISTANCE. IN THE 4.5 MODEL THE CONTACT WILL BE LESSER THAN BICON LIKE MODEL AND THE GAP ALSO START TO BECOME HIGHER	192
FIGURE 78 MODEL OF 9 DEGREES ANGLE CONTACT PRESSURE. THE CONTACT START BE 2 SEPARATED REGIONS	193
FIGURE 79 GAP OF THE MODE 9 DEGREES IS MUCH HIGHER THAN THE 2 PREVIOUS MODELS. THE GAP TEND TO HAVE ONE CONTINUOUS REGION	194
FIGURE 80 MODEL OF 20 DEGREES ANGLE CONTACT PRESSURE	195
FIGURE 81 GAP OF THE MODE 20 DEGREES IS MUCH HIGHER THAN THE PREVIOUS MODELS. THE GAP IN THE FORCE APPLICATION SITE AND OTHER SIDE BECOME CONTINUOUS	196
FIGURE 82 CONTACT PRESSURE OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	197
FIGURE 83 THE GAP OF 45 DEGREES MODEL IS TOTALLY DIFFERENT FROM THE OTHER MODELS	198
FIGURE 84 CONTACT PRESSURE OF THE FLAT MODEL (BRÅNEMARK MODEL)	199
FIGURE 85 GAP OF THE FLAT MODEL. WE MUST ALWAYS EMPHASIZE THE PATTERN OF DISTRIBUTION AND CONNECT IT TO OTHER EVALUATION CRITERIA TO GET THE WHOLE PICTURE	200
FIGURE 86 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH BICON LIKE MODEL. THIS IS PARTIALLY DUE TO CONFIGURATION OF THE BOUNDARIES CONDITIONS OF THE USED MODEL	202
FIGURE 87 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH 4.5 DEGREES MODEL . THE IMPLANT ABUTMENT GRIPPING WILL PROTECT THE SCREW FROM THE PLASTIC CHANGE BY FORCING THE IMPLANT BODY TO DEFORM WHICH IS EQUAL TO MORE STRESS TRANSFER FROM ABUTMENT TO THE ABUTMENT	203
FIGURE 88 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH 9 DEGREES MODEL. THE STRAIN ALONG ALL THE SIDE OF THE SHAFT	204
FIGURE 89 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH 20 DEGREES MODEL	205
FIGURE 90 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH 45 DEGREES MODEL	206
FIGURE 91 1 ST PRINCIPAL STRAIN WITH FLAT LIKE DESIGN	207
FIGURE 92 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE BICON LIKE DESIGN LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION.	208
FIGURE 93 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE 4.5 DEGREES ANGLE LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	210
FIGURE 94 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE 9 DEGREES ANGLE LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	211
FIGURE 95 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE 20 DEGREES ANGLE LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	212
FIGURE 96 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE 45 DEGREES ANGLE LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	213
FIGURE 97 THE V MISES STRESS OF THE FLAT DESIGN VARIANT LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	214
FIGURE 98 TRANSITION OF THE STRESSES IS APPARENT ACROSS ALL THE MODEL. THE MODEL ON THE LEFT IS THE BICON LIKE MODEL THEN THE 9 DEGREES MODEL THEN THE 20 DEGREES MODEL THEN THE ORIGINAL PLATFORM MATCHING MODEL. WE HAD NOT REPRESENTED THE 4.5 AND 45DEGREES MODELS.	215
FIGURE 99 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL. IN THE BICON LIKE MODEL THE SHAFT OF THE CONNECTING SCREW IS VERY SHORT	216
FIGURE 100 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL	217
FIGURE 101 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 9 DEGREES MODEL	218

FIGURE 102 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	219
FIGURE 103 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	220
FIGURE 104 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE CONNECTING SCREW SHAFT OF THE 89 DEGREES MODEL	221
FIGURE 105 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN BICON LIKE DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	222
FIGURE 106 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN 4.5 DEGREES DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	223
FIGURE 107 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN 9 DEGREES DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	224
FIGURE 108 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN 20 DEGREES DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	225
FIGURE 109 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN 45 DEGREES DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	226
FIGURE 110 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT BODY IN 89 DEGREES DESIGN WITH LATERAL FORCE AND ROTATION	227
FIGURE 111 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE BICON LIKE DESIGN	228
FIGURE 112 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL	229
FIGURE 113 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE 9 DEGREES MODEL	230
FIGURE 114 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	231
FIGURE 115 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	232
FIGURE 116 CURL OF THE DISPLACEMENT, Z COMPONENT OF THE 89 DEGREES MODEL. WE HAD COMPARED BETWEEN THE ROTATION ACTION ONLY OF 4.5 AND 9 AND 20 DEGREES MODEL	233
FIGURE 117 ROTATION OF THE MODELS FROM RIGHT TO LEFT 4.5 DEGREES 9 DEGREES 20 DEGREES. THE DISPLACEMENT IS HIGHER WITH THE HIGHER ANGLE AND LESS UNIFORM	234
FIGURE 118 ROTATION OF THE IMPLANT MODEL ONLY MODELS FROM RIGHT TO LEFT 4.5 DEGREES 9 DEGREES 20 DEGREES. THE DISPLACEMENT BECOMES MORE UNIFORM AND HIGHER WITH THE LESS ANGLE	234
FIGURE 119 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE SHAFT OF THE CONNECTING SCREW INDICATING THE POSSIBLE SCREW LOOSENING DUE TO THE ROTATION OF THE MODELS FROM RIGHT TO LEFT 4.5 DEGREES 9 DEGREES 20 DEGREES.	235
FIGURE 120 THE 2 ND PRINCIPAL STRAIN OF THE IMPLANT ONLY FROM THE CASE OF THE FROM RIGHT TO LEFT 4.5 DEGREES 9 DEGREES 20 DEGREES. INDICATING THE HIGHER ABILITY OF THE ABUTMENT TO ROTATE THE IMPLANT WITH LESS SCREW LOOSENING RESULTS. THESE RESULTS INDICATE THE MORE ROBUST IMPLANT ABUTMENT CONNECTION IN STRESSES TRANSMISSION	235
FIGURE 121 Y FIELD OF DISPLACEMENT OF THE MODELS FROM RIGHT TO LEFT 4.5 DEGREES 9 DEGREES 20 DEGREES THE LESS IS THE BETTER. WE HADN'T MODELED THE Y FIELD OF DISPLACEMENT OF ONLY IMPLANT	236
FIGURE 122 STRAN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE BICON LIKE DESIGN	237
FIGURE 123 STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 4.5 DEGREES MODEL	238
FIGURE 124 STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 9 DEGREES MODEL	239
FIGURE 125 STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	240
FIGURE 126 STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	241
FIGURE 127 STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 89 DEGREES MODEL	242

FIGURE 128 THE TRANSITION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DISTRIBUTION IN THE DIFFERENT DESIGNS IS APPARENT. THE 2 ND AND 3 RD MODEL HAD MARKED 2 WALLS INVOLVEMENT. THE LAST DESIGN ACT AS A LEVER WITH SOLE RESISTANCE THAT IS DERIVED FROM THE CONNECTING SCREW. THE INCREASE IN THE ANGLE OF THE CONE COINCIDES WITH INCREASE IN THE ENERGY DENSITY IN THE CONNECTING SCREW	243
FIGURE 129 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE BICON LIKE MODEL	244
FIGURE 130 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 4.5 MODEL	245
FIGURE 131 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 9 DEGREES MODEL	246
FIGURE 132 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 20 DEGREES MODEL	247
FIGURE 133 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 45 DEGREES MODEL	248
FIGURE 134 3D REPRESENTATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY OF THE 89 DEGREES MODEL	249
FIGURE 135 IN THE LAST FIGURE THE ABSENCE OF THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY AT THE OUTERMOST REGION OF THE UPPER SURFACE AWAY FROM THE REGION OF THE CONTACT WITH THE ABUTMENT INDICATE THE DELETERIOUS EFFECT OF THE COMPRESSION CAME FROM THE ABUTMENT	250

References

1. *Platform switch and dental implants: A meta-analysis.* Chrcanovic BR, Albrektsson T, Wennerberg A. s.l. : J Dent., 2015;43(6):629-646.
2. *Platform-Switching Concept in Dental Implants: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials with a Minimum Follow-up of 3 Years.* Mishra SK, Gaddale R, Sonnahalli NK, Chowdhary R. s.l. : Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants., 2021.
3. *Comparative Study by Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of the Peri-Implant Effect of Two Types of Platforms: Platform-Switching versus Conventional Platforms.* Juan-Montesinos, A., et al. s.l. : J. Clin. Med., 2022, 11, 1743.
4. *A suggested design for a tissue level dental implant. .* Alhamdani F, Al-Ghali B. s.l. : Asian J Oral Health Allied Sci, 2021;11:3.
5. *Role of Platform Switching in Success of Dental Implants- A Meta-Analysis.* s.l. : Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, 14(4), 1506-1515., (2020).
6. *Effects of Platform-Switching on Peri-implant Soft and Hard Tissue Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis.* Hsu YT, Lin GH, Wang HL. s.l. : Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants., 2017;32(1):e9-e24.
7. Jimenez-Lopez, de Vicente. *Immediate Loading In Implant Dentistry: Surgical, Prosthetic, Occlusal, And Laboratory Aspects.* s.l. : Quintessence Pub Co, 2005. ISBN-10 : 848987333X.

8. Tribst, J.P.M., et al. *The Effect of Implant–Abutment Contact Area on the Stress Generation of Bone-Level and Tissue-Level Implants*. s.l. : Appl. Sci., 2025, 15, 2744.
9. Topkaya, Tolga & Solmaz, Murat & Dundar, Serkan & Eltas, Abubekir. *Numerical analysis of the effect of implant geometry to stress distributions of the three different commercial dental implant system*. s.l. : Cumhuriyet Dental Journal. , (2015).
10. Bäcker HC, Wu CH, Kienzle A, Perka C, Gwinner C. *Mechanical failure of total hip arthroplasties and associated risk factors*. s.l. : Arch Orthop Trauma Surg., 2023 Feb;143(2):1061-1069.
11. *Titanium-Titanium Junctions in the Knee Corrode, Generating Damage Similar to the Hip*,. Michael A. Kurtz, Shabnam Aslani, James A. Smith, Gregg R. Klein, Hannah Spece, Steven M. Kurtz,. s.l. : The Journal of Arthroplasty,, 2024.07.026.
12. *Effect of the spline region faces number in the polygonal design on the performance of the Titanium dental implants, an important matter we overlook*. Saadoon, M. Z. s.l. : International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), (2025).
13. *Impact of platform switching implants on crestal bone level: A systematic review and meta-analysis*,. Majedeh Nami, Hazhir Maslahaty, Benika Abbasi, Morteza Sharifi, Atiyeh Farahi, Nazieh Abdollah Kookhi,. s.l. : The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry,, 2025.03.007.
14. H. Dong. *Surface Engineering of Light Alloys*,. 2010.

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.